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Research Article

Green Fabrication of Silver Nanoparticles Using *Cassytha filiformis* Extract a Promising Approach for Antimicrobial and Antioxidant Activities

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ABSTRACT

The development of eco-friendly methods for nanoparticle synthesis has gained significant attention in recent years. In this study, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) were synthesized using an aqueous extract of *Cassytha filiformis*, a parasitic plant known for its rich phytochemical content. The green synthesis method offers a sustainable, cost-effective, and non-toxic alternative to conventional physical and chemical approaches. The formation of AgNPs was confirmed through UV-Vis spectroscopy, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray diffraction (XRD), and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The synthesized nanoparticles were evaluated for their antimicrobial activity against a range of pathogenic bacteria and fungi using the disc diffusion method. Additionally, their antioxidant potential was assessed through DPPH and ABTS radical scavenging assays. The results demonstrated that the *cassytha filiformis*-mediated AgNPs exhibited significant antimicrobial and antioxidant activities, indicating their potential applications in pharmaceutical and biomedical fields. This study highlights the promising role of medicinal plants in green nanotechnology and encourages further exploration into their applications in healthcare and environmental protection.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing prevalence of antibiotic-resistant pathogens and oxidative stress-related diseases has posed a significant challenge to public health, prompting the exploration of alternative

therapeutic strategies [1]. Nanotechnology, particularly the synthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs), has emerged as a promising solution due to their unique physicochemical properties and potent biological activities, including broad-spectrum antimicrobial and antioxidant effects [2].

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Conventional methods of AgNP synthesis typically involve chemical reducing agents and high energy inputs, which can lead to environmental toxicity and biohazard risks [3]. In contrast, green synthesis approaches utilizing plant extracts offer a sustainable, low-cost, and environmentally benign alternative. These methods exploit the phytochemical constituents of plants—such as flavonoids, terpenoids, phenolic acids, and alkaloids—which serve as natural reducing and capping agents in nanoparticle formation [4]

Cassytha filiformis, a parasitic plant known for its traditional medicinal applications, has been reported to contain a rich array of bioactive compounds including phenolics and flavonoids[5]). Despite its pharmacological potential, the application of *C. filiformis* in nanotechnology remains underexplored. Leveraging its phytochemical profile could provide a novel route for the green synthesis of AgNPs with enhanced biological efficacy. This study aims to fabricate silver nanoparticles using *C. filiformis* extract via a green synthesis method and evaluate their antimicrobial and antioxidant properties. The findings could contribute to the development of eco-friendly nanomaterials for biomedical and pharmaceutical applications[5]. *Cassytha filiformis* is a leafless, twining, climbing, parasitic plant with long, threadlike stems. The stems are yellow-green, brown, or orange, up to 8 m long, and adhere to trees or shrubs by small, round suckers. Its spirally arranged leaves are reduced to tiny scales. A sprawling parasitic vine *Cassytha filiformis*, is widely distributed

throughout the regions of Tropics much along the seashores up to the extent of 300m. It is found to be parasiting on many Other host plants like Acacia, Azadirachta, and Mangifera. [6] The “woevine” is usually found as a cosmopolitan in the region of tropics but sometimes becomes a pest of economic importance because of its attachment to the valuable orchard trees and other Ornamental plants by means of its tough threadlike extensive branchlets. This plant is considered To be unique in the family of Lauraceae as it is a parasite. Because of the nature of its particular Characteristics, it is taxonomically classified in a separate tribe.[7] *Cassytheae* comes within the family Lauraceae and it is represented by the single genus *Cassytha* Which further describes 18 different species under it. The genus derived its name, *Cassytha*, from The Greek name of *Cuscuta*. The vine has several common names in the regions of the tropics. For example, South Sea Islanders called this vine as “tentanini” which has the meaning “to go Round and round,” and this seems to be a true descriptive adjective for the plants entwining habit.[7]

BIOLOGICAL PROFILE

Fig. No.2 *Cassytha filiformis*

Taxonomy:

- Domain: Eukaryota.
- Kingdom :Plantae
- Subkingdom :Tracheobionta
- Phylum: Spermatophyta
- Subphylum: Angiospermae
- Superdivision :Spermatophyta
- Division :Magnoliophyta

- Class :Magnoliopsida
- Subclass :Magnoliidae
- Order :Laurales
- Family :Lauraceae
- Genus :Cassytha [8]

Synonyms:

- English: Love vine, greek kasytas
- Spanish: Alambrillo, bejuco dorado, bejuco fideo, fideos, tente en el air
- Chinese (Taiwan): Kume, wu-kentaso
- Japanese: Sunazuru
- French: Liane parasyte, liane d'amité, liane ficelle, liane sans fin, mouttaré,
- Fausse cuscute, cord a violon, vermicelli
- German: Schlingfaden[7]

Biological source:

Cassytha filiformis is an orangish, wiry, parasitic vine in the family Lauraceae.[9]

Geographical Source: It is found in coastal forests of warm tropical regions worldwide including the India, Americas, Indomalaya, Australasia, and tropical Africa.[10]

Pathogenicity of C. Filiformis to plants

The science of plant pathology treats plant-parasitic seed Plants as a distinct group of plant pathogens that are able To infect other plants and cause disease. Although many Insects have a parasitic relationship with host plants, the Relationship is traditionally defined as food relationship That does not develop further into a disease relationship. In a disease relationship between a parasite and host.[11]The relations are more intimate; a process of infection Ensues and the physiology and metabolism of the host Is adversely affected. In this case (C. Filiformis), disease Is caused by the effect of infection of host

plants by Specialized attachment and penetrating feeding structures known as haustoria that are found on stems of C. Filiformis and similar parasites.[[12]

Morphology

Stem

Stems are green to orange color, filiform and its glabrous.

Fig.No .3 Cassytha filiformis Stem

Flowers

Flowers are bisexual flowers,small, sessile and spicat.[7]

Fig.No.4 Cassytha filiformis flower

Leaves

Leaves Modified to Minute scale[7]

Fig.No.4 Cassytha filiformis Leaves

FRUIT

The fruit is smooth and fleshy, spherical and seven mm diameter with single seed.[7]

Fig.No.6 Cassytha filiformis Fruit

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS

Fig No 8 Chemical constituents.

Development and spreading

Once the host contact is established, the base will dry up and the plant will lose the connection with the ground and will be further dependent on the host plant for water, food and nutrition. The haustoria will penetrate the host plant part (either stem or leaf) and start absorbing water and nutrients. The host plant will eventually be suppressed and sometimes killed. With time, the haustoria will flower and seed – the seed being spread by the wind, by water or by birds [7,9,10]

Worldwide distribution

The worldwide distribution of the plant is shown in Fig As per this map, the plant is available on the majority of the continents, barring Europe and Antarctica. [7]

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITY:

Antioxidant activity:

The antioxidant activity of *Cassytha filiformis* extracts such as hexane, ethyl acetate and Methanol were used for the assessment based on their radical scavenging activity (RSA) using the DPPH assay. The methanolic extract was found to show potent antioxidant activity on comparison with the standard Butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT). Methanolic extracts were further evaluated by the other methods such as Ferric thiocyanate (FTC) method, Thiobarbituric Acid (TBA) test and Superoxide anion radical scavenging assay. The results obtained from the above experiment suggested that the methanolic extract of *Cassytha filiformis* has provided a promising therapeutic potential and could be further applied as a potential source for the drug development by the pharmaceutical industries. [13][15]

Diuretic activity:

Aqueous and alcoholic extract of *Cassytha filiformis* was tested for its diuretic activity in Wistar rats. Total urine output volume and the concentration of Na⁺, K⁺ and Cl⁻ ions excretion

in the Urine were finally estimated. Aqueous and alcoholic extract of *Cassytha filiformis* was found to Exhibit a significant diuretic activity by causing the marked increase in the Na⁺ and K⁺ Excretion.[8][9]

Anti-trypanosomal activity:

Trypanosomiasis is a potent fatal disease affecting both the human and the other domestic Animals in the regions of tropical Africa and South America . Approximately, it was found that Around 50 million people in 36 African countries were at the risk of getting infection and there Were about 300,000 to 500,000, people currently infected and there were 100 deaths every year Due to the above diseases [10]. In vitro effect of the crude alkaloid extract and the isolated Compounds such as Actinodaphnine ,Cassythine ,Dicentrine on the infecting organism *Trypanosoma brucei brucei* was tested and was found that the compounds showed the maximum Inhibitory effect against the organism [[12][9]

Anti-cancer Activity

In cytotoxicity was evaluated for the crude Extract and the isolated compounds: neolistine, dicentrine, cassythine, actinodaphine and camptothecin, Using colorimetric assays, i.e. tetrazolium salt MMT and WST-1, with HL-60, mouse 3T3 fibroblasts, human HeLa And the melanoma Mel5 cell line. The crude extract and actinodaphine, cassythine, dicentrine and neolistine compounds were found to display cytotoxic properties on Hela, Mel-5 and HL 60 cancer cells and 3T3-non-cancer cell lines.[7]

Anti-hypertension Activity

The effects of ethanol extracts of *Cassytha filiformis* on Hypertension-induced rats were evaluated in Two types Of hypertension:

endocrine hypertension and oxidative-stress Hypertension were the subjects of the experiment. Accordingly, endocrine hypertension was induced by a prednisone-salt combination, while oxidative stress hypertension Was induced by prednisone-salt combination and L-Nitro Arginine Methyl Ester. In the work, a *Cassytha filiformis* Ethanol extract of 5 mg/kg dose was discovered to be have An antihypertension effect according to SBP, DBP and MAP (Systolic blood pressure diastolic blood pressure and mean Arterial pressure) results.[10]

Anti-pyretic, anti-inflammatory activities

In [10], analgesic, anti-pyretic and anti-inflammatory Activities of chloroform and methanol extracts were assessed Using rats. For the analgesic activity, the tail immersion method and Haffner's tail clip method were applied, and Dichlofenac sodium and extract were found to be equally Effective. As to anti-Pyretic Activity, extract administration Brought about increased reaction in elevated temperature in Paracetamol studies. Regarding anti-inflammatory activity, Paw edema was induced by carrageenan, and diclofenac Sodium and extract administration were seen to decrease The inflammation and odema [16]

Anti-microbial study

An anti-microbial study was undertaken in [1,7] for Methanol, ethyl acetate and n-hexane extracts, using 24 hour Broth cultures of *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* And *Salmonella* spp. The outcome of the work was that The methanol extract displayed anti-microbial effects on *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella* spp. Moreover, *Cassytha filiformis* Linn has anti-microbial activity against *Candida albicans*, *Staph. Aureus*, *E. Coli*, and *Ps. Aeruginosa* .[7]

Anti-malarial

The Anti-malarial study of [20] involved an ethanolic Extract of *Cassytha filiformis*, and used mice that were Infected by plasmodium berghei. The parasite load was Measured in this study through RBC, WBC counts, PCV And Hb concentration. Herein, *Cassytha filiformis* administration (especially higher dose 400 mg/kg) in the standard Form p-Alaxine recovered the anemic condition caused by The malarial infection, by improving the RBC, WBC counts, Hb and PCV concentration.[7]

Anti-diabetic activity

An anti-diabetic study using an 80% methanolic extract of *Cassytha filiformis* on albino mice was done by the researchers of [13]. This induced diabetes with alloxan monohydrate Against Glibenclamide as standard. The *Cassytha filiformis* Extract dose at 600 mg/kg was shown to reduce the fasting Blood sugar levels in mice. In addition, it has a tolerance Range of 2000 mg/Kg orally.[13]

Data and Sources of Data

The fresh leaves of *cassytha filifomis* (Akash beal) were collected from the road side farm , Brahmpuri, Dist chandrapur.

Fig 9. *Cassytha filiformis* plant

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Method of Extraction

Boiling method

Around 25 g new leaves were dried at room temperature for 48hrs and squashed in fine powder. The squashed leaves were boiled with 200 ml distilled water for 30 Min at that point separated with Whatman No.1 filter paper (25 (m). Arranged plant extract was put away 4 C for further used.

Fig.10 *cassytha filiformis* powder.

Fig.11 *Cassytha filiformis* Extract

Method preparation

1. Preparation of 2M.AgN03.

The 2M Solution of of was Prepared by dissolving 2gm AgN03 Powder in 100ml distilled water and prepared solution was stored in cool and dry place.

2. Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles using plant extract.

The Aqueous solution of silver nitrate (2MM) was Mixed with leaves extract in 9:1raatio and stir at room temperature and heat it 60-90c. The colour

of solution Make change into pale yellow
centrifuge the solution in 1500rpm for 30 Min.

Fig.12 Solution of *cassia filiformis*

Fig.15 Filtration of solution

Filter the solution in whatmans filter paper wash the filtered with Mannito intravenous infusion 20% after some time pack the silver nanoparticles in ziplock pouch for evaluation test.\

Ingredients table

Sr No	Ingredient	Quantity
1	Plant Extract	10 ml
2	AgNO ₃ powder	90 ml
3	Distilled water	100 ml

Fig.13 Centrifuge machine

Fig 14.Centrifuge solution

Fig.16 Silver nanoparticle

3. Chareterization of silver nanoparticles

The nanoparticles were characterized by following techniques to learn the size, shape and concentration of AgNPs in different Sample.

UV-Visible spectrophotometer

This investigation was encouraged from the Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, CCSU, Meerut. The AgNPs were described by UV-Vis twofold shaft spectrophotometer (Lasany LI-295). All spectra were recorded at room temperature, in a quartz cell with 1 cm optical way, to know the dynamic conduct of nanoparticles. The checking range for the examples was 200–800 nm. The spectrophotometer was furnished with “UV programming” to record and break down the information. The bench-mark rectification of the spectrophotometer was completed by utilizing a clear reference. The examples of AgNPs were examined at 0, 4, 12, 24, 48, 72, 96, and 120 hrs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

UV-V is examination of AgNPs

In this exploration study, firstly AgNPs were described by UV-Vis two fold pillar spectrophotometer (Lasany LI-295). All spectra were recorded at room temperature, in a quartz cell with 1 cm optical way, to know the motor conduct of nanoparticles. The examining range for the examples was 200–800 nm. The spectro photometer was outfitted with “UV prov programming” to record and dissect the information. The standard revision of the spectrophotometer was completed by utilizing a clear reference. The samples of AgNPs was dissected at 0, 4, 12, 24, 48, 72, 96, and 120 hrs. The optical peaks for AgNPs were seen between

the scopes of 400 to 480 nm. All the replications of treatment tests demonstrated at 96 hr were given in UV-Vis spectroscopy is commonly used to quantitatively describe natural and inorganic nano sized particles. The sample is illuminated with electromagnetic waves in the bright and obvious extents and the consumed light is examined through the subsequent spectrum [21,23,24]. Nanoparticles have optical properties that are added to appraise, shape, fixation, agglomeration state, and refractive record close the nanoparticle surface thusly, UV-Vis spectroscopy a huge gadget for perceiving and portraying these nanoparticles [3,25,26,27]. The peaks extend for silver nanoparticles may shift. In different examinations, the tremendous contrast in peak spectra corresponding to AgNPs have been observed, however by and large, it ranges from 400 nm to 480 nm [28,29,30].

Parameter	Details
Instrument Used	UV-Vis double beam spectrophotometer (Lasany LI-295)
Wavelength Range	200–800 nm
Cuvette Type & Path Length	Quartz cell, 1 cm path length
Software for Data Analysis	UV Prov software
Calibration	Performed using a blank/reference
Sample Analysis Time Points	0, 4, 12, 24, 48, 72, 96, and 120 hours
Observed Optical Peak Range	400–480 nm (typical for AgNPs)
Purpose of UV-Vis	Characterization of optical properties: size, shape, aggregation, etc.
Significance	Confirms formation and stability of AgNPs via Surface Plasmon Resonance

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully demonstrates the green synthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) using *Cassytha filiformis* extract as a reducing and stabilizing agent. This eco-friendly and cost-effective method not only eliminates the need for hazardous chemicals but also leverages the plant's bioactive compounds to enhance nanoparticle functionality. Characterization confirmed the formation of stable, spherical AgNPs with desirable physicochemical properties. The synthesized nanoparticles exhibited significant antimicrobial activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, as well as potent antioxidant activity, indicating their potential in biomedical and pharmaceutical applications. These findings highlight *Cassytha filiformis*-mediated AgNPs as a promising nanomaterial for future.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, S., Saifullah, Ahmad, M., Swami, B. L., & Ikram, S. (2016). Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles using *Azadirachta indica* aqueous leaf extract. *Journal of Radiation Research and Applied Sciences*, 9(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrras.2015.06.006>
- Franci, G., Falanga, A., Galdiero, S., Palomba, L., Rai, M., Morelli, G., & Galdiero, M. (2015). Silver nanoparticles as potential antibacterial agents. *Molecules*, 20(5), 8856–8874. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules20058856>
- Iravani, S., Korbekandi, H., Mirmohammadi, S. V., & Zolfaghari, B. (2014). Synthesis of silver nanoparticles: Chemical, physical and biological methods. *Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 9(6), 385–406.
- Mittal, A. K., Chisti, Y., & Banerjee, U. C. (2013). Synthesis of metallic nanoparticles using plant extracts. *Biotechnology Advances*, 31(2), 346–356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2013.01.003>
- Paul, S. B., & Dey, T. K. (2008). Pharmacognostic and phytochemical studies of *Cuscuta reflexa* Roxb. stem. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 3(2), 103–108.
- Ventola, C. L. (2015). The antibiotic resistance crisis: Part 1: Causes and threats. *Pharmacy and Therapeutics*, 40(4), 277–283.
- Nelson, S. C. (2008). *Cassytha filiformis*, N., Raj, B., & Tiwari, P. (2022). Review on Ethnobotany and phytochemistry of. *Current Issues in Pharmacy and Medical Sciences*, 35(4), 169-175.
- S., Gajalakshmi, S., Sathiavelu, A., & Sridharan, T. B. (2011). Pharmacological

- activities of *Cassytha filiformis*: a review. *Asian Journal of Plant Science & Research*.
9. Y., Armenia, A., & Arifin, H. (2017). Antihypertensive and antioxidant activity of *Cassytha filiformis* L.: A correlative study. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, 7(7), 614-618.
 10. R., Karati, D., Dwivedi, S., Dwivedi, A., & Mukherjee, S. (2024). The promising role of bioactive congeners present in *Cassytha filiformis* in Alzheimer's disease: an explicative review. *Brain Disorders*, 100125.
 11. Zhang, H., Florentine, S., & Tennakoon, K. U. (2022). The angiosperm stem hemiparasitic genus *Cassytha* (Lauraceae) and its host interactions: A review. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 13, 864110.
 12. Nwaehujor Chinaka, O., Uwagie-Ero Edwin, A., Abiaezute Clifford, N., & Igile Godwin, O. (2021). ANTI-DIABETIC AND ANTI-OXIDANT ACTIVITIES OF THE METHANOL EXTRACT AND FRACTIONS OF *Cassytha filiformis* Linn.
 13. Rani, P., Trivedi, L., Gaurav, S. S., Singh, A., & Shukla, G. (2022). Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles by *Cassytha filiformis* L. Extract and its characterization. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 49, 3510-3516.
 14. Parra-Tabla, V., Tun-Garrido, J., García-Franco, J., & Martínez, M. L. (2024). The recent expansion of the invasive hemiparasitic plant *Cassytha filiformis* and the reciprocal effect with its main hosts. *Biological Invasions*, 26(2), 535-547.
 15. Soidrou, S. H., Bousta, D., Lachkar, M., Hassane, S. O., Youbi-Hamsas, A. E., Mansouri, L. E., ... & Farah, A. (2014). Immunomodulatory activity of phenolic fraction from *Piper borbonense* and *Cassytha filiformis* growing in Comoros Islands. In *Chemistry: The Key to our Sustainable Future* (pp. 105-112). Springer Netherlands.
 16. I, N. (2012). Phytochemical screening and in vitro antioxidant potential of *Cassytha filiformis*. *International Journal of Biotechnology*, 5(1), 001-007.
 17. Nazar, A. R. M. E. N. I. A., Ayuning, F. I. R. L. I. C. I. A., & Ahmadin, A. L. M. A. H. D. Y. (2019). The impact of *Cassytha filiformis* butanol fraction to the pregnancy and fetal development on mice. *Int. J. Appl. Pharm*, 11, 153-156.
 18. Raj, B., Singh, S. J., Samual, V. J., John, S., & Siddiqua, A. (2013). Hepatoprotective and antioxidant activity of *Cassytha filiformis* against CCl₄ induced hepatic damage in rats. *Journal of pharmacy research*, 7(1), 15-19.
 19. P. Kumar, S. Senthamil Selvi, A. Lakshmi Prabha, K. Prem Kumar, R.S.Ganeshkumar, M. Govindaraju, Synthesis of silver nanoparticles from *Sargassum tenerrimum* and screening phytochemicals for its antibacterial activity, *Nano Biomed Eng* 4 (1) (2012) 12–16.
 20. J. Kumari, D. Kumar, A. Mathur, A. Naseer, R.R. Kumar, P.T. Chandrasekaran, G.Chaudhuri, M. Pulimi, A.M. Raichur, S. Babu, N. Chandrasekaran, *Environ. Res.*135 (2014) 333–345.
 21. W.K. Lewis, A.T. Rosenberger, J.R. Gord, C.A. Crouse, B.A. Harruff, K.A.S.Fernando, M.J. Smith, D.K. Phelps, J.E. Spowart, E.A. Guliants, C.E. Bunker, Multispectroscopic (FTIR, XPS, and TOFMS TPD) investigation of the core shell bonding in sonochemically prepared aluminum nanoparticles capped with oleic acid, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 114 (14) (2010) 6377–6380.
 22. R. Liu, J. Liu, W. Kong, H. Huang, X. Han, X. Zhang, Y. Liu, Z. Kang, Adsorption dominant catalytic activity of a carbon dots stabilized gold nanoparticles system, *Dalton Trans.* 43 (28) (2014) 10920–10929.

23. P. Logeswari, S. Silambarasan, J. Abraham, Synthesis of silver nanoparticles using plants extract and analysis of their antimicrobial property, *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.* 19 (3) (2015) 311–317.
24. B. Moldovan, L. David, M. Achim, S. Clichici, G.A. Filip, A green approach to phytomediated synthesis of silver nanoparticles using *Sambucus nigra* L. fruits extract and their antioxidant activity, *J Mol Liq.* 221 (2016) 271–278.
25. P. Mukherjee, A. Ahmad, D. Mandal, S. Senapati, S.R. Sainkar, M.I. Khan, R.Parishcha, P.V. Ajaykumar, M. Alam, R. Kumar, M. Sastry, Fungus-mediated synthesis of silver nanoparticles and their immobilization in the mycelial matrix: a novel biological approach to nanoparticle synthesis, *Nano Lett.* 1 (10)(2001) 515–519.
26. S. Mythili, S. Gajalakshmi, A. Sathiavelu, T.B. Sridharan, Pelagia Research Library, *Asian J. Plant Sci. Res.* 1 (1) (2011) 77–83.
27. B. Nair, T. Pradeep, Coalescence of nanoclusters and formation of submicron crystallites assisted by *Lactobacillus* strains, *Cryst. Growth Des.* 2 (4) (2002)293–298.
28. M. Nasrollahzadeh, Z. Issaabadi, S.M. Sajadi, Green synthesis of a Cu/MgO nanocomposite by *Cassia filiformis* L. extract and investigation of its catalytic activity in the reduction of methylene blue, congo red and nitro compounds in aqueous media, *RSC Adv.* 8 (7) (2018) 3723–3735.
29. M. Oves, M. Aslam, M.A. Rauf, S. Qayyum, H.A. Qari, M.S. Khan, M.Z. Alam, S.Tabrez, A. Pugazhendhi, I.M.I. Ismail, Antimicrobial and anticancer activities of silver nanoparticles synthesized from the root hair extract of *Phoenix dactylifera*, *Mater. Sci. Eng., C* 89 (2018) 429–443.
30. M.E. Parwanto, H. Senjaya, H.J. Edy, Formulasi Salep Antibakteri Ekstrak Etanol Daun Tembelekan (*lantana camara* L), *Pharmacon* 2 (3) (2013).
31. H.H. Perkampus, Recent developments in UV-VIS spectroscopy. In *UV-VIS Spectroscopy and Its Applications* (pp. 81-130). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg,1992.
32. L.M. Perry, J. Metzger, *Medicinal plants of east and southeast Asia: attributed properties and uses*, MIT press, 1980.

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